

Introduction to Drone Technology for Agriculture Purposes: A Brief Review

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Abstract

Decades ago, drones developed for the uses of the military as they without a human pilot and can save more lives during war and battlefield. With the technology transformations in this recent year, drones are expanding their application to other areas such as photography, environment, and agriculture. Special features and facilities fitted to the drone such as HD cameras, GPS, tracker, smart sensors and others to enhance the drone's functions. As for agriculture, companies and fellow researchers uncover the drone technology and developing it for agriculture purposes to overcome challenges faced by the farmers to produce better crop yields. Drones are one of the excellent approaches to improve the crop by aerial monitoring, analyzing and spraying. The technology of drones and its purposes for agriculture that was uncovered by fellow researchers will be compiled and reviewed on this paper hoping that it could bring advantages, especially to farmers to ease their difficulties.

Keywords: Drone, UAV, Agriculture, Spraying system

1 Introduction

Over hundreds of years ago, the development of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) or commonly known as drones started to be used in the war and battlefield. These drones were created for military purposes and intelligence agencies in the year of 1800s. The difference between drones and other aircraft is that drones do not carry any human pilot. They are controlled remotely by on the ground human pilot operator or they fly freely with software guided plans equipped in their systems.

Currently, there are thousands of drones used worldwide in a variety of applications such as photography, military, agriculture and many more. Drones also integrated with functions that can reach beyond human limitations. Drones can fly high up to 400 meters in the sky to get the best picturesque natural landscape pictures. A hobbyist drone equipped with HD cameras to capture sharp images, GPS and tracker to fly in larger distances beyond the human eye distance and even portable LCD that can be remotely controlled.

As the technology of drones increasing, the threat of drones also increases. This includes the injury that occurs related to drone flying. Reported cases of drone-related injuries such as skull fracture, blunt trauma, amputation, and others are mostly caused by drone parts such as propellers or rotors and struts. The drone operator should follow the safe and guide for drone flying to avoid injuries to the operator, public, and property damage.

The applications of drones are expanding from military and hobbyists to industries such as agriculture. Currently, drones that are developed specifically for the uses of agriculture are out in the market. There are varieties of features that fitted with facilities to help the farmers overcome challenges for better crop production. With the help of a drone, the agriculture industry can be less difficult to handle for both large and small crops.

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Thus, this review presents a compilation of several studies and finding that revealed the technology of drones and how drones can be an excellent approach for the agriculture industry.

What Is Drone?

2.1 History of Drones

Drones are the most common names as in the early years it is known as flying robot ^[1]. A formal description of drones is an unmanned aircraft system that remote-controlled pilot-less. As the drone flying soar up in the air, the best thing about drones that they are flying without any human or people inside controlling it. The human pilot that controls the drone by an onboard computer on land where sometimes who's called an operator ^[2].

Fig. 1 Timeline of the development of drones in the early years

The name drones acquired from the honeybee drones where the bees are doing their task unconditionally (mindlessly) because they are controlled by the mighty queen in a faraway ^[3]. Amazingly, the drone works the same way as the bees as they are being microcontroller programmed by the operator to be on autopilot and the innovation of the drone keeps expanding with the aid of technology.

As the timeline in **Fig. 1** shows, the earliest use of drones recorded in 1849, known as the Austrian balloons where they attacked Venice, Italy with a pilotless balloon armed with bombs. Then, the use of drones progressed as in World War I in 1916, the Ruston Proctor Aerial target used and followed by the Hewitt-Sperry Automatic Airplane that popularly known as "flying bomb" ^[4]. The innovation increases as in 1929, Gipsy Moth produced in the United Kingdom. A successor of the Gipsy Moth then created named de Havilland Tiger Moth as radio controls are put on the drone. The final product of the evolution is the DH82B Queen Bee as it was the first returnable and reusable UAV that was used as practice targets. As the drone is widely used for military purposes, the Vietnam War also affected by the rising of drone technology. The roles of drones not only as explosive loaded but also work as combat's decoy, missiles launching on fixed targets and spreading leaflets for psychological techniques ^[1]. Target Drone Denny 1 or shorted as TDD1 was a drone that contract signed by the US Navy. Their roles were as an actor and radio control model aircraft. TDD1 are the first instance of the name "drone" are being associated with unmanned remotely piloted vehicle ^[3].

2.2 Type Of Drones

There are various types of drones available in the market. Some experts categorized the drones based on their weight and flight range. In Table 1, the categorization of drones proposed based on their weight started from micro and mini drones that weigh less than 5kg with a flight range of 25km to 40km ^[5]. The super heavy drones or combat aircraft weighs more than 500kg and can fly in the range of 1500km. Other experts grouped the drones based on the physical properties such as the number of propellers or rotors and based on the purposes

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of drones such as surveillance, aerial photography, engineering, construction, and entertainment. Table 2 shows the categorization proposed where the drones grouped by their number of propellers or rotors ^[3].

Table 1 Categorization of drones based on their weight and flight range ^[6]

Drone Properties	Weight Range	Flight Range
Micro and mini UAVs close range	$W \leq 5 \text{ kg}$	$25 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 40 \text{ km}$
Heavy medium-range UAVs	$500 \text{ kg} \leq W$	$70 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 300 \text{ km}$
Unmanned combat aircraft	$500 \text{ kg} < W$	$R \leq 1500 \text{ km}$
Lightweight UAVs medium range	$50 \text{ kg} < W \leq 100 \text{ kg}$	$70 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 250 \text{ km}$
Lightweight UAVs small range	$5 \text{ kg} < W \leq 50 \text{ kg}$	$10 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 70 \text{ km}$
Medium heavy UAVs	$300 \text{ kg} < W \leq 500 \text{ kg}$	$70 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 300 \text{ km}$
Heavy UAVs large endurance	$1500 \text{ kg} \leq W$	$R \leq 1500 \text{ km}$
Average UAVs	$100 \text{ kg} < W \leq 300 \text{ kg}$	$150 \text{ km} \leq R \leq 1000 \text{ km}$

Table

2

Categorization of drones by number of rotors or propellers ^[3]

Type of Drones	Properties	Example
Single rotor drones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -helicopter look alike -heading controlled by the small rotor on the tail -simple and scalable easily 	
Tricopters (Three rotors or propellers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -has 3 motors for light use -compact, foldable, lighter -can carry small load only for camera 	
Quadcopters (Four rotors or propellers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the most famous multicopters -faster, easy to manufacture, affordable -4 propellers to lift up the aircraft -great maneuverability, thrust, and power -can be fixed easily and available readily in the market 	
Hexacopters (Six rotors or propellers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -upgraded from quadcopter -can fly high up with expensive cameras -high speed, high power, fly higher due to six rotors -120 degrees apart motors that can pick up the slack if one of the motors dies -more expensive than quadcopters -difficult to fly in small spaces due to large size -motor parts are very expensive 	
Octocopters (Eight rotors or propellers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -same benefits with hexacopters but with more speed and power -fly higher to capture sharp capture images and footages -have 8 motors and propellers -cannot be hindered by wind or rain -if the 2 or 3 motors dies, the craft will not be crashing down - very large and expensive 	

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Fixed-wing drones -have wings like common airplanes
-use for long-distance fly, mapping, monitoring, and agriculture
-have a higher cost and special training needed to handle the aircraft

2.3 Recommended Safety and Precautions Operating Drones

The popularity of recreational drones has been increasing in the last decade ^[7]. Almost 2 million recreational or hobbyist drones being sold in 2016 and around 4 million will be sold expectedly in 2020 ^[8]. As the sale increases, drone-related injuries also increasing and several cases were published as the injuries are getting serious ^[9]. For example, a 13-year-old boy struck by a racing drone and cause him to suffer a depressed skull fracture ^[10] and a 9-year-old hit by unprotected propellers and suffered an ocular globe rupture ^[11]. Approximately almost 12 842 recreational drone injuries were registered to the U.S emergency department in the year 2010 to 2017. From these total injuries, 74.2% were recorded suffered injuries caused by propellers and rotors. The injury can lead to lacerations and amputations of injured body parts such as fingers and hands ^[7].

Drone-related injury can occur not only to the drone operator himself but also to the public and can lead to general damage to property. To avoid any injury to the drone operator, personal protective equipment (PPE) must be worn all time when handling the drone. A hard hat can protect the head from falling drones while safety goggle protects the eyes from shattered propellers ^[4]. A high visibility vest with a reflective label can be seen easily and identified especially handling the drones in the crowd. To avoid injuries to the public, the drone operator must only fly on the designated area with signage to aware others of the drone operations. The designated area must be physical restraint by barricading the area using drone nets or chain tape ^[5]. To protect property damage, the drone must-have safety features on risky components. For example, the propellers must be from plastic material instead of carbon fiber because it can cause scratch or dent to the property if hits ^[11]. The propeller must have guards to protect both the propellers and the surrounding. The drone operator often advised to always bring a first aid kit and a fire extinguisher in case of fire or explosion ^[7].

2.4 Application of Drone

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Fig. 2 Application of drone classification ^[6]

The uses of drones cover both in the military and civil sectors. One of the purposes of drones is that can reach beyond human limitations. They can fly indoor or outdoor flight zone in very challenging conditions ^[12]. Various sensors, cameras, and system attached to different types of drones to enhance their functionality for surveillance, reconnaissance and intelligence missions ^[13]. Drones application can be grouped to a different type of missions, flight zone, and environment. **Fig. 2** shows the flow chart of drones’ applications according to researchers ^[14, 15].

Experts predicted that drones may have more than two hundred functions according to their type in the future ^[13, 14]. For example, micro-drones that are equipped with a camera can provide images and videos even in the darkness. In the battlefield, only small size drones can be used to view inside a building and detect any nuclear, biological weapon or other threats ^[16]. As in civil applications, the drones are being used in many creative ways. In Rwanda, they use drones to deliver medications while in New Zealand, drones fly to deliver pizza and take aerial photographs for popular realtor websites ^[3]. The innovation of drones’ application widens in the agriculture, film, deliveries, engineering and other sectors.

2.41 Drones In Videography/Photography

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In movies or films, the use of drones is very common as they use drones equipped with high-quality cameras that can capture footage and scenes from above and give more real impact to the film. The production companies can save up to thousands of dollars in making a film by using drones [17]. Instead of using the cameraman to fly up high to capture scenes, the usage of drones also can prevent human casualties. In photography, drones can be a business tool for wedding photography, corporate videos, video editing and many more. Some used drones as a hobby to take scenic photography beyond human reach [18]. Real estate sites use drones to capture panoramic views such as homes, lands, and skyscrapers because, from high altitude, regular photography was impractical [19].

Fig. 3 Istanbul district shot from the sky [18]

Fig. 4 Cappadocia scene shot from the sky [18]

2.42 Drones in Environment and Climate

Even though drones are an essential tool in the military sector, they are also increasingly being used to perform environmental missions. For example, national parks and reserve forests can be managed by drones easily, wildlife can be tracked in various ranges, the impact of climate change can be uncovered and numerous flora and fauna can be discovered from oceans to rainforest worldwide [20]. Drones also can detect and investigate natural catastrophes such as bush fires, disasters on hill and mountains and others [21, 22]. Table 3 shows researchers have been using drones to control the population and climate change in the year 2018 where the technology of drones started to widen in the environment application.

Table 3 Research studies conducted by using the drone for environment and climate

Year	Research Purposes	Reference
2018	Monitoring aquatic environment using drone-based fluorosensor	[23]
2019	Research on turtles and other marine vertebrates using drones	[24]
2020	Modeling of outdoor microclimate using infrared assisted drone	[25]
2020	Beach litter assessment by commercial aerial drone	[26]
2020	Monitoring visual and acoustic behavior of gray whales in Mexico by using two drones	[27]

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Fig. 5 Research studies conducted in the agriculture sector

3 Drones and Agriculture

Over the years, drones develop the expectation of a large turning point in the way people grow crops. By depending on the technology of drones, precision agriculture can be accomplished while resolving water and food crisis^[28]. Precision agriculture can be defined as the management of crop that involves GPS and big data^[29]. Lately, drones have been helping the farmers increase crop yield using their abilities. For example, drones can capture, remodel and analyze leaves individually on corn plants by flying from 120 meters height, getting some soil capacity of water-holding to variable-rate water application and delivering agriculture intelligence for both farmers and agricultural consultants^[30]. The development of the drone in agriculture application concerns assisting both small and large farming operations.

The Association of Unmanned Vehicle International reported that the legalization of commercial drones will be predicted to create more than €70 billion in economic impact in a decade from the year 2015 to 2025^[31]. In the prediction, precision agriculture will provide a large part of economic growth. **Fig. 5** shows the proportion of research studies conducted by using drones in agriculture but with a different type of applications.

It can be seen that drone application in agriculture consists of aerial pesticide or fertilizer spraying, crop monitoring and a few others. 60% of the papers referred to deal with aerial spraying.

Aerial spraying has many potentials especially in Asia countries such as South Korea, China, and Japan. In 1997, Japan developed UAV spraying to cover thousands of hectares of forestry and crop. Yamaha Corporation (Japan) initiate the pilotless helicopter for agricultural purposes. Later in 2007, the export of the helicopters is banned to avoid being used by others^[32]. The unmanned helicopters then named Yamaha R-MAX and currently, Yamaha offers services to interested farmers instead of selling the unit. On the other hand, China has developed the idea of the unmanned helicopter into a foldable octocopter with smart flight mode, carbon fiber materials and compact called DJI Agras MG-1^[33]. DJI is one of the large companies in China that build drones and monopolized the market by producing all types of drones from micro to heavy-duty drones. Inspired by both countries, many researchers developed their unmanned drones for agricultural purposes. Table 4 and Table 5 shows the features and specifications of the Yamaha helicopter, DJI drones, and other researchers' agriculture drones.

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Product	Manufacturer	References
<u>Agras</u> MG-1 DJI	DJI (China)	[34]
Yamaha RMAX	<u>Yahama</u> Corporation (Japan)	[35]
Drone mounted sprayer	-	[36]
6-rotor UAV	-	[37]
N-3 UAV	-	[38]
3WQF120-12	Anyang <u>Quanfeng</u> Aviation Plant Protection Technology Co., Ltd. (China)	
3CD-15	Wuxi <u>Hanhe</u> Aviation Technology Co., Ltd (China)	[39]
WSZ-0610	Shandong <u>Wish</u> Plant Protection Machinery Co., Ltd. (China)	
HY-B-15L	Shenzhen High-tech New Agricultural Technology Co., Ltd. (China)	

Table 4 Drones for spraying in agriculture

Table 5 Features and specifications of drones for spraying in the agriculture sector

Properties	Agras MG-1 DJI	Yamaha RMAX	Drone mounted sprayer	6-rotor UAV	N-3 UAV	3WQF120-12	3CD-15	WSZ-0610	HY-B-15L
Maximum speed	8 m/s	-	-	16 m/s	4 m/s	5 m/s	6 m/s	4 m/s	4.5 m/s
Flight time duration	-	1 hour	-	25 min	-	50 min	30 min	40 min	35 min
Vehicle weight	8.8 kg	100 kg	6 kg	10 kg	-	-	-	-	-
Number of nozzles	4	-	4	4	2	2	4	2	5
Type of nozzle	-	-	Flat fan	Electrostatic	Rotary atomizer	LUI20-02	Flat fan 01	Centrifugal atomizer	2 Flat fan and 1 cone
Tank capacity	10 L	16 L	5 L	10 L	25 L	12 L	15 L	10 L	15 L
Rotor diameter	-	3.1 m	-	-	3.2 m	2.41 m	2.24 m	2.22 m	2.46 m
Number of rotors	8	1	6	6	1	1	1	6	1

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Vehicle length	1471 mm	2750 mm	420 mm	1500 mm	-	-	-	-	-
Vehicle height	482 mm	1080 mm	450 mm	600 mm	-	-	-	-	-
Vehicle width	1471 mm	720 mm	1300 mm	400 mm	-	-	-	-	-
Cost per vehicle	\$ 15 000	\$120 000	-	-	-	\$32 000	\$35 000	\$13 000	\$27 000

5 Conclusions

The uses of drones are widening to a variety of applications and industries including agriculture. There are more than can be discovered through the technology of drone from its features, specifications, and facilities that can bring significant technology transformations, especially to the agriculture application. With the hope that this paper can be an eye-opener to fellow researchers and others to develop and integrate more drones to overcome the agriculture challenges better and increase the crop yield better in the future.

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